

Using Building Information Modeling (BIM) for Environmental Simulation: Improving Sustainable Design Considerations in Residential Buildings

TAKYALDEEN ALARMOUTY

Supervisors:

Lavinia Chiara Tabliabue

Computer Science Department, University of Turin, Corso Svizzera 185, 10149 Turin, Italy

Abstract

Building Information Modeling (BIM) represents a transformative paradigm shift within the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) domain, affording an integrated digital framework for the holistic management of building lifecycles, encompassing design, construction, operation, and maintenance phases. A prominent hallmark of BIM lies in its capacity to empower environmental simulations, thereby furnishing designers with the instrumental capability to scrutinize and optimize building performance across dimensions pertinent to energy efficiency, indoor environmental quality, and sustainability. This thesis conveys a scholarly investigation centered on the utilization of BIM for environmental simulation, specifically within the purview of sustainable design considerations vis-à-vis residential structures.

The study's methodology involves a comprehensive literature review of sustainable building design principles, the role of building envelope design in achieving sustainable buildings,

material selection and resource efficiency, design considerations for promoting good indoor environmental quality, and strategies for optimising energy performance. The study also analyses rating systems and standards, such as LEED, PEER, EDGE, WELL, and ICP, and their applicability to sustainable design considerations in residential buildings.

The study's results demonstrate the effectiveness of BIM for environmental simulation in improving sustainable design considerations in residential buildings. The study presents case studies of residential building design using environmental simulation, including daylight simulation, energy simulation, indoor air quality and ventilation simulation, and acoustic simulation. The study also emphasises the importance of life cycle perspective and the use of Virtual Design and Construction (VDC), Internet of Things (IoT), and Digital Twin technologies for enhanced construction efficiency and sustainability.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/fL-oRggSUX0>

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